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Internal report:

The Higher Education Standardisation of Gender Equality, Digital and Green Skills in EU Policy Documents

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The aims: This report provides an overview of policies on gender equality and digital and green skills as represented in EU policy documents, with particular emphasis on standardisation in higher education.

The structure (content): The first section for each key concept presents a brief definition of critical concepts established by EU green, digital and gender equality policies regarding standardisation: gender equality in standardisation, gender-responsive standards, sustainability and standardisation, European leadership in standardisation, digital skills for standards professionals. The second section presents an overview/analysis of how these concepts appear in the EU policy documents.

The Scope:

Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG), 2015; Strategic Engagement for Gender Equality 2016-2019; Strategic Framework for European Cooperation in Education and Training (ET 2020), European Commission's Strategy for Equality between Women and Men (2020-2025), Decision (EU) 2023/936 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 on a European Year of Skills European Commission, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, Key competencies for lifelong learning, Publications Office, 2019, Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006, European Union, European Commission (2020). Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: EU Gender Action Plan (Gap) III – an Ambitious Agenda for Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in EU External Action, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, An EU Strategy on Standardisation - Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green and digital EU single market (2022) Digital Education Action Plan (2020-2027) EU Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp) European Skills Agenda for Sustainable

Competitiveness (2020) European Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience (2020), and European Green Deal (2019)

Main Findings: The EU's strategy for standardisation acknowledges the need for new skills in response to technological challenges and horizontal considerations such as artificial intelligence, data protection, and cybersecurity. However, it does not specifically address certain skills for standardisation. While digital skills are not explicitly defined within the Strategy, the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens outlines critical elements of digital competencies across five areas, identifying 21 specific competencies (DigComp 2.2, 2022). The EU policy on standardisation emphasises the urgency of preparing new standardisation specialists to replace the retiring generation of experts. It also highlights the necessity of building bridges between the research, innovation, and standardisation communities (An EU Strategy on Standardisation, 2022, p.8-9).

The EU's industrial strategy views the development of green and digital skills as a strategic investment in the workforce, crucial for Europe's recovery and the strengthening of the Single Market. This strategy, however, does not mention gender equality (Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a Stronger Single Market for Europe's Recovery, COM/2021/350 Final, p.20). The EU education strategy identifies business, law, and engineering as fields of study that require the integration of standardisation into their curricula. EU policies on standardisation advocate for gender equality by recommending balanced representation of men and women in organisations, developing gender-responsive standards, eliminating biases, and ensuring that the needs of both women and men are met. While green and digital skills are highlighted in the EU's green and digital strategies as essential for the green and digital transition, these skills are not explicitly detailed in the context of standardisation. The reviewed policy documents provide specific objectives and examples of how desired skills can be promoted through education, but they do not directly address the education of standardisation specialists. Overall, the task of standardisation aims to position the EU as a global leader in setting standards for modern technologies and upholding democratic values.

1. Adopted Definitions: The List Of The Most Important Definitions

Digital Skills: Individuals should be able to use digital technologies to support their active citizenship and social inclusion, collaboration with others, and creativity towards personal, social or commercial goals. Skills include the ability to use, access, filter, evaluate,

create, program and share digital content. Individuals should be able to manage and protect information, content, data, and digital identities and recognise and effectively engage with software, devices, artificial intelligence or robots (p.10 of Key competencies for lifelong learning¹).

Green skills: Knowledge, abilities, values and attitudes needed to live, work and act in economies and societies seeking to reduce the impact of human activity on the environment.

Skills for the green economy consist of the following:

- Transversal skills linked to sustainable thinking and acting, relevant to all economic sectors and occupations;
- Specific skills required to adapt or implement standards, processes and services to protect ecosystems and biodiversity and to reduce energy, materials and water consumption;
- Highly specialised skills are required to develop and implement green technologies such as renewable energies, sewage treatment or recycling (according to Terminology of European Education and Training Policy²).

Gender equality: Equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities of women and men and girls and boys. Equality does not mean that women and men will become the same but that women's and men's rights, responsibilities and opportunities will not depend on whether they are born female or male³. Gender equality implies that the interests, needs and priorities of both women and men are considered, thereby recognising the diversity of different groups of women and men. Gender equality is not a women's issue but should concern and fully engage men as well as women. Equality between women and men is seen as a human rights issue and a precondition for an indicator of sustainable people-centred development.

Well-being: Subjective well-being refers to how people perceive the quality of their lives. European Foundation for Improvement of Living and Working Conditions defines three categories of well-being:

- Evaluative well-being – life satisfaction and satisfaction with domains of life

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, *Key competences for lifelong learning*, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2766/569540>

² Terminology of European education and training policy <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/vet-glossary/glossary>

³ Promoting Gender Equality: An Equity-based Approach to Programming https://www.unicef.org/gender/files/Overarching_2Pager_Web.pdf

- Positive and negative affect – happiness, vitality, feeling calm, feeling cheerful, feeling depressed
- Eudaimonic well-being consists of optimism, autonomy, a sense of purpose, time to enjoy life, and resilience (according to the European Quality of Life Survey⁴).

2. Gender Equality

Gender equality is a core value of the EU, a fundamental right and a vital principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights. It is also essential for an innovative, competitive and thriving European economy. “In business, politics and society as a whole, we can only reach our full potential if we use all of our talent and diversity”⁵. EU treaties emphasise that the Union should work to eliminate gender inequalities and promote transversal equality in all its activities. The European Council recalls that ‘mainstreaming the principle of equality between women and men in all its activities represents a general aim for the Union. By integrating the gender perspective into all policy areas, gender mainstreaming is also considered a tool to promote and reinforce good governance. The Treaty of Lisbon reaffirms the EU's commitment to promoting gender equality as a fundamental principle. Article 2 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU) states that the EU is founded on freedom, democracy, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, and the rule of law, including the principle of gender equality⁶.

Mainstreaming Gender Equality in Higher Education Policies: The EU encourages Member States to mainstream gender equality principles into their higher education policies and strategies. This involves integrating gender equality objectives into funding programs, quality assurance mechanisms, and institutional development plans. The EU's efforts contribute to promoting gender equality in and through quality, affordable and inclusive education at all levels, building more muscular gender-responsive education systems to promote gender equality and deliver more equitable education results for girls and boys through

⁴ **European Quality of Life Survey**

https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/data-catalogue/european-quality-life-survey?load_page=ReportSection531f02309ca830c77084

⁵ See Articles 2 and 3(3) TEU, Articles 8, 10, 19 and 157 TFEU and Articles 21 and 23 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT>

⁶ TREATY OF LISBON AMENDING THE TREATY ON EUROPEAN UNION AND THE TREATY ESTABLISHING THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (2007/C 306/01)
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A12007L%2FTXT>

safe and healthy learning environments, teacher recruitment, training and professional development, curriculum, and learning materials, increasing investment in girls' education to ensure equal access across all educational domains, including STEM fields, digital literacy, and technical and vocational training. 1) Robust measures to counteract gender stereotypes, discriminatory social norms, and instances of gender-based violence within educational settings, supporting research and data collection on gender imbalances in higher education to inform policy development and monitoring efforts (pp.13-14 of the EU GENDER ACTION PLAN (GAP) III⁷).

Many countries have shown significant improvements in equalising educational opportunities for men and women, according to the EU Gender Equality Index 2023⁸. Besides, the EU member states have developed various tools and practices to support the inclusion and equal opportunity of students, researchers and staff from diverse backgrounds in European R&I systems⁹. Gender equality in higher education is a priority area for the European Union (EU), and several policy documents and initiatives address this issue. Here are some key EU policy documents related to gender equality in higher education:

- **The European Higher Education Area (EHEA):** While not a specific policy document, the EHEA promotes gender equality as one of its core values. It emphasises the importance of ensuring equal opportunities for all individuals in higher education, regardless of gender.
- **Strategic Framework for European Cooperation in Education and Training (ET 2020):** This framework sets out strategic objectives and priorities for education and training in Europe. Gender equality is highlighted as a cross-cutting priority, focusing on promoting equal access, participation, and success for women and men in education, including higher education.
- **The European Commission's Strategy for Equality between Women and Men (2020-2025)** outlines the EU's approach to advancing gender equality across

⁷ European Union, European Commission (2020). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: EU Gender Action Plan (Gap) III – an Ambitious Agenda for Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in EU External Action*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020JC0017&from=EN>

⁸ Gender Equality Index
https://eige.europa.eu/modules/custom/eige_gei/app/content/downloads/factsheets/EU_2023_factsheet.pdf

⁹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Approaches to inclusive gender equality in research and innovation (R&I)*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/004694>

various sectors, including education. It emphasises the importance of addressing gender stereotypes, promoting women's participation in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics), and combating gender-based discrimination in education, including higher education.

- **European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers:** These documents promote gender equality in research and higher education institutions. They encourage institutions to create a supportive and inclusive environment for all researchers, regardless of gender, and to implement gender equality measures in recruitment, career development, and work-life balance policies.

- **Horizon Europe:** The EU's framework program for research and innovation, Horizon Europe, includes specific objectives and funding opportunities to promote gender equality in research and innovation. This includes supporting research projects that address gender inequalities and promoting women's participation in research and innovation activities, including those conducted in higher education institutions. These plans typically include measures to support women's career progression, improve work-life balance, and prevent gender-based discrimination and harassment.

Gender Equality Plans: EU advocates for gender equality plan to be adopted and implemented in universities and other higher learning institutions to eliminate gender stereotyping for women's career progression.

The pillars of gender equality policies are the following:

- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Standardisation defines ways of working and establishes norms for measuring progression towards accomplishing goals and objectives on gender equality in higher learning institutions. This may entail compiling and analysing data on gender distribution, productivity, career advancement, and engagement to identify disparities and determine the success of gender mainstreaming policies and approaches.

- **Capacity Building and Training:** Measures of promotion may also include provision of support, training and other forms of support to HEIs, staff and

students to enhance the institution's commitment to gender equality and diversity. This may entail organisational learning approaches, such as workshops, seminars, and professional development of the faculty and students in gender-sensitive instruction and research, gender mainstreaming, stereotyping and bias, and gender-sensitive leadership.

- **International Collaboration and Exchange:** The EU promotes the exchange of information and knowledge between HEIs, policymakers, and other stakeholders at the national and EU levels. This may involve participation in networks, working groups and projects on women's promotion in higher learning institutions, information sharing and benchmarking, and learning about what has worked well in other settings.

3. Gender Equality And Standardisation

According to ISO Standard 26000, Guidance on Social Responsibility, organisations are recommended to have a balanced mix of men and women in governing structures and management, ensure both sexes are treated equally when it comes to recruitment, career opportunities, and pay, and ensure the needs of men and women are given equal consideration in company decisions and activities to promote parity and eliminate bias.

In addition, ISO strives to promote equal representation in standardisation, increase women's participation in the development of ISO International Standards, and improve standardisation for women worldwide. The ISO 53800 Standard is being developed to tackle this goal: guidelines for promoting and implementing gender equality and women's empowerment.

While ISO 53800 does not feature the necessary skills for the incorporation of gender equality into standardisation, it establishes the following benefits:

- Promote a comprehensive understanding and implementation of gender equality
- Support the creation of inclusive and equitable organisational cultures
- Encourage gender equality as a fundamental human rights issue
- Aids organisations in fulfilling legal obligations regarding gender equality.

One more direction of ISO and IEC efforts towards gender equality is the development of gender-responsive standards. Thus, experts are recommended to develop/obtain, as required, the skills and expertise needed to create and implement a gender action plan.

- **Gender-Responsive Standards: ISO-UNECE, 2022, A Joint Initiative by ISO and UNECE:** Building upon the UNECE document, the ISO-U case on gender-responsive standards goes further in providing specific guidelines and case studies. The present document stresses the role of international cooperation in advancing gender equality through standardisation and offers several examples of gender-sensitive standards that have been introduced. One of the pillars of this approach is the focus on elaborating and adopting gender action plans in standardisation bodies. These plans are intended to provide a progressive approach to integrating the consideration of gender in all phases of the standardisation process. This includes establishing measurable goals for gender equality, defining concrete steps towards achieving these goals, and evaluating the progress through periodic evaluations and reviews.

The document also examines how gender audits can be conducted in standardisation organisations. Gender audits are assessments undertaken to determine to what level gender aspects are incorporated into organisational systems and products. Gender audits help organisations to find out where changes are required, and remedial measures are put in place to make the organisation gender-responsive. Also, the initiative points out the need to incorporate gender disparities when setting standards for the use of data. Gathering and comparing data on how standards affect men and women can help understand how standards influence people differently. It can then assist in creating better standards that will consider the needs of all genders.

- **Green Skills and Knowledge: Defining ESCO (UNECE, 2022):** The paper Green Skills and Knowledge: labelling within the ESCO (UNECE) framework is dedicated to the relationship between environmental sustainability and skills. This paper aims to illustrate the need for training and educating the workforce to prepare them for the green transition, which is imperative for the EU to meet its environmental objectives. This paper identifies and describes critical green skills necessary in various fields, such as renewable energy, energy efficiency and sustainable resource management. For this reason, these skills are vital in fostering innovation in green technologies and practices that can help minimise carbon emissions in society. The document aims to standardise the recognition of green competencies by labelling these skills within the ESCO framework so employers can easily attract suitable candidates with the appropriate skills.

One of the critical elements of the document is the focus on learning and training throughout the working career. Regarding the green transition, there will be an increasing need for new and emerging skills as the process advances. The document emphasises the importance of continuing education and training in light of these workforce changes. This includes the incorporation of green skills in conventional education and training systems as well as in the development of new programs with an emphasis on sustainability. Also, the role of certification and accreditation in the development of green skills is presented in the document. The UNECE also seeks to enhance the quality of green skills training by developing standards and accredited certification in green competencies. It can foster more confidence among employers and other relevant stakeholders to invest in green training and education.

- In early 2024, the Commission published a study on the inclusiveness of anthropometric provisions in harmonised European standards¹⁰. This assessment aimed to determine whether the standards that have an anthropometric dimension sufficiently consider the diversity of the European population, including factors such as gender and age, and the various anthropometric measurements (e.g. height, weight and strength).

4. Digital Skills

The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2009) defines digital skills as “a range of abilities to use digital devices, communication applications, and networks to access and manage information”. These abilities make creating and sharing digital content possible, communicating and collaborating with others, solving problems, and finding creative opportunities. Similarly, the Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Life-long Learning defined digital competence as ‘the confident, critical and responsible use of, and engagement with, digital technologies for learning, work, and participation in society. It is defined as a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

¹⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, (2024). *Study on the inclusiveness of anthropometrics in European harmonised standards : final report*, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/172248>

There is a strong link between digital skills and key competencies enabling lifelong learning. European citizens should be equipped with critical skills needed for an increasingly digital world: the ability to filter, use, access, or manage private data, personal information, and one's digital footprint, stay safe online, and effectively use technologies like AI and other software. People should also 'be able to use digital technologies to support their active citizenship and social inclusion, collaboration with others, and creativity towards personal, social, or commercial goals' (European Commission, 2019). This concept of digital skills is more concerned with European citizens than ICT professionals' specialised skills. The EU framework for citizens' digital competence (DigComp) outlines the digital skills citizens need to remain competitive in the labour market, socialise, shop, and learn in today's digital world.

Several EU policy documents address digital skills as a critical training and workforce development priority. Here are some notable ones:

- Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027): This action plan aims to support the digital transformation of European education and training systems. As stated in Priority one, this action plan supports digital transformation through Erasmus Cooperation projects for all levels of education, enhances pedagogy and expertise in using digital tools for teachers through Erasmus Teacher academies and launches an online self-assessment tool for teachers, SELFIE for Teachers. It includes initiatives to improve digital skills among students, educators, and other stakeholders, promote digital literacy and citizenship, and foster innovation in digital education.
- Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition: The Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition is a multi-stakeholder partnership launched by the European Commission to promote digital skills and employment in Europe. As stated on page 3, everyone needs digital skills not only to work but also to take part in society. With the introduction of ever more sophisticated digital technologies, having sufficiently skilled people to develop and use these technologies is essential. Today, only 57% have the digital skills needed for our digital world. One in six Europeans aged 16-74 had no digital skills, and one in four only had low-level digital skills. It brings together governments, businesses, education providers, and civil society organisations to take action on digital skills development through various initiatives, campaigns, and funding programs¹¹.

¹¹ Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-skills-coalition>

- New Skills Agenda for Europe: The New Skills Agenda for Europe sets a framework for improving the quality, relevance, and effectiveness of skills development in Europe. It includes initiatives to promote digital skills and digitalisation across different sectors, support lifelong learning and upskilling, and address digital divides and inequalities. The workforce demands of the future call for skills for dual transformations. The green transition also entails investment in the skills of people to create more experts who are involved in making green technologies such as digital technologies, developing green products, services and business models, as well as creating nature-based solutions to reduce impacts on the environment of all activities (p.12).
- European Skills Agenda for Sustainable Competitiveness, Social Fairness and Resilience: The European Skills Agenda presents a clear roadmap for preparing people for today's and future occupations. It covers measures to increase digital literacy, encourage vocational education and training, develop digital assets, and promote digital advancement and business.

The above-discussed policy reveals the EU's vision to close the digital skills gap, support digital literacy, and provide people with the necessary competencies for the digital era. They offer a structure that enables national governments, education institutions, employers, and other parties to work in unison and address the need for digital skills promotion in Europe. Policies on digital skills development in higher education within the European Union (EU) are defined by the following strategies and initiatives: Using digital technologies in teaching and learning more effectively, Acquiring appropriate digital capabilities and knowledge for digital learning, and Enhancing education by using data more effectively.

- **Digital Competence Frameworks**: The EU has created models like the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp) and the DigCompEdu¹² model for learners to identify the digital literacy skills and abilities essential for employment, education, and social life in the contemporary world. These frameworks provide a standard reference for higher education institutions to design curricula, develop learning outcomes, and assess students' digital competencies.
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According to the Digital Education Action Plan, the following initiatives are included¹³: Integrating digital skills and competencies into higher education curricula across different disciplines and fields of study. This may include offering courses, modules, or programs focused on digital literacy, information technology, data analysis, programming, cybersecurity, digital communication, and digital citizenship.

- **Assessment and Certification:** Standardisation efforts include developing common assessment methods and criteria to evaluate students' digital skills and competencies effectively. This may involve using standardised tests, rubrics, portfolios, or digital badges to assess students' proficiency in various digital domains and provide them with recognised certifications or credentials upon completing digital skills training programs.

- **Professional Development for Educators:** Standardisation entails providing professional development to enhance educators' ICT competencies and content knowledge on how best to incorporate ICTs in teaching and learning. It can entail offering workshops, training, and interest groups dealing with areas like integrating technology in the teaching-learning process, distance education, LMS, and e-assessment.

- **Quality Assurance and Accreditation:** Standardisation is geared towards the quality and relevance of training in digital skills training programmes offered in higher learning institutions through quality assurance and accreditation. This may involve ensuring that the digital skills curricula taught in the institution match the current market needs, evaluating the digital learning activities from time to time and seeking recognition from the right authorities.

According to the Terminology of European Education and Training Policy, curriculum development is designing, improving, organising and planning educational or training activities¹⁴. Overall, EU policies on digital skills development in higher education seek to equip students with the digital competencies they need to thrive in a rapidly changing digital world,

¹³ Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027 Resetting education and training for the digital age <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0624>

¹⁴ Education, Training and Youth. (n.d.). European-Union.europa.eu. https://european-union.europa.eu/priorities-and-actions/actions-topic/education-training-and-youth_en#:~:text=The%20EU%20sets%20out%20the

enhance the quality and effectiveness of digital learning experiences, and foster innovation and competitiveness in higher education.

5. Green Skills

The European Classification of Occupations, Skills and Competences (ESCO) responded to this call to action. ESCO skills and knowledge concepts needed to live in, develop and support a society that reduces human activity's environmental impact (Cedefop, 2012) are now labelled as green. This report provides information concerning the labelling process and guides ESCO implementers in their use of ESCO green concepts.¹⁵

- **Green Skills Index:** The Green Skills Index is a metric used to assess the availability, relevance, and development of skills related to sustainability and environmental stewardship within a given context, such as a country, region, or industry sector.
- **Availability of Green Skills:** This includes educational programs, training courses, and initiatives focused on sustainability, environmental conservation, renewable energy, and other green topics. As the European Skills Agenda states on p.12, the focus is on "boosting the supply of green skills to meet the demand in various sectors." These are offered by schools, universities, vocational training centers, employers, government agencies, and non-profit organizations.
- **Relevance of Green Skills:** This assesses how well the skills being taught align with the current and future needs of the labor market and society regarding sustainability. As the European Skills Agenda states, the importance of aligning skills with "the needs of the green transition and the evolving labor market" (p. 15). It evaluates whether training programs cover vital topics, address emerging trends and challenges, and meet industry standards and certification requirements.
- **Development of Green Skills:** This pertains to the effectiveness of measures to promote green skills among students, workers, and professionals. As the European Green Deal states, "investing in education and training to equip people with the skills required for the green transition" is essential (p. 20). It includes learning

¹⁵ Green Skills and Knowledge Concepts: Labelling the ESCO classification

<https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/about-esco/publications/publication/green-skills-and-knowledge-concepts-labelling-esco>

outcomes, acquired skills and expertise, participation rates, and satisfaction levels of green skills training.

These policy documents provide a framework for promoting digital and green skills in higher education and guide EU member states in implementing strategies to address these priorities. Higher education institutions are encouraged to align their curricula, teaching methods, and research activities with the objectives outlined in these policy documents to prepare students for the digital and green economy of the future:

- European Skills Agenda for Sustainable Competitiveness, Social Fairness and Resilience (2020): This document outlines a plan to improve European skills and employment, emphasizing the digital and green economy. The agenda states there is a need for "re-skilling and up-skilling to support the green and digital transitions"¹⁶ It points out the necessity of education and training to meet the labour market's needs, emphasising digital and green skills in tertiary education.

- European Green Deal: While not explicitly targeting education, the European Green Deal aims to transform the EU's economy to be more environmentally friendly. It recommends promoting green skills and innovation in higher education institutions, integrating sustainable development and environmental issues into academic curricula and research priorities.¹⁷ The deal states, "education and training systems must be fit for the green transition" (p. 15). Within this framework, efforts are made to encourage integrating sustainable development and environmental issues into higher learning institutions' academic curricula and research priorities.

- Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition: This is an action plan of the European Union that calls for the participation of government, business, and educational institutions in promoting the development of e-skills in Europe.

These dimensions can be measured using several quantitative and or qualitative measures that may be used to develop the Green Skills Index¹⁸, such as the number of green

¹⁶ European Parliament TEXTS ADOPTED P9_TA-PROV(2021)0051 European Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience. (2019).

<https://www.engineerseurope.com/sites/default/files/European%20Skills%20Agenda.pdf>

¹⁷ European Commission. (2020). *The European Green Deal*. European Commission.

https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

¹⁸ Arthur, C. (2022, August 8). What are green skills? | UNIDO. Wwww.unido.org.

<https://www.unido.org/stories/what-are-green-skills>

occupational classifications, the number of employees trained for sustainable development, the amount of money invested in education and training on sustainability, the demand in green skills according to employers and greening self-reported beliefs and practices among employees. Consequently, the Green Skills Index is an analytical tool that offers an overview of green skills and the opportunities and threats inherent in the given context; it also outlines the prospects for improving green skills and building human capital necessary to address environmental issues.

According to the European Commission's Recommendations and Strategies on Sustainable Development and Environmental Policies, EU Framework Programs for Research and Innovation, European Commission's Communications and Directives on Education and Skills Development, Reports and Publications from the European Parliament, European Council, and European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), Documentation from EU-funded projects and initiatives focused on sustainability education and green skills training in higher education, the main aspects of EU policy regarding green skills in higher education are the following:

- Integration of Sustainability into Curricula: EU policies promote the idea of mainstreaming sustainability principles, concepts, and practices in higher education institutions for all fields of study offered in tertiary institutions, covering environmental conservation, climate change, energy, sustainability, and corporate responsibility. They emphasize "mainstreaming sustainability in all curricula and educational programs."
- Promotion of Interdisciplinary Approaches: EU policies support the use of a combination of disciplinary approaches in teaching and learning about sustainability. This includes promoting interdisciplinary cooperation within academic units to deliver interdisciplinary courses, research, and programs encouraging "cross-disciplinary cooperation to tackle complex environmental challenges."
- Experiential Learning and Practical Skills Development: EU policies focus on one key approach that stresses the necessity of teaching and enhancing green skills within students through practical activities. This may involve providing students with internships, field trips, and other forms of experiential learning where the students are able to hone the practical skills required to solve sustainability problems.

- Partnerships with Industry and Stakeholders: EU policies promote cooperation of higher education institutions with industry, government, other non-profit organizations, and other partners in order to define requirements for new green skills and develop corresponding training¹⁹. This may encompass "partnerships between educational institutions and industry to develop relevant green skills".
- Promoting Lifelong Learning and Continuous Professional Development: EU policies encourage citizens to be lifelong learners and to continue to upgrade their knowledge and skills in sustainable development. This includes providing professional development for professionals to acquire more training occasionally and brush up on their green skills, awareness and readiness in the new context through training programs, short courses, workshops, and seminars.
- Recognition and Certification of Green Skills: EU policies promote effective learning and qualification of green skills in both formal and informal settings. This may include the innovation of qualification frameworks, standards, and certification programs for green careers, as well as the encouragement of the validation of non-formal and experiential learning in volunteering, internships, and community engagement.

Overall, EU policies for higher education introduce green skills as a response to environmental challenges and fostering sustainable development, as well as green skills as preparation for a green work environment and jobs for students. To make higher education institutions attain these goals, it is possible to advance sustainability within teaching, learning, interdisciplinary cooperation, practical training, and involvement of stakeholders.

Final Summary

Although the documents outline policies that comply with the European social model of participation, environmental responsibility, and intelligent development, they do not provide guidelines on how to incorporate gender equality into curriculum of higher educational institutions.

¹⁹ *Promoting higher education*. (n.d.). Neighbourhood-Enlargement.ec.europa.eu. https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/european-neighbourhood-policy/promoting-higher-education_en

The critical analysis of the gaps revealed in the digital, green skills related to standardisation and the approaches to the gender equality require the development of a new curriculum model. Some techniques employed while designing curricula in green skills for higher learning institutions include curriculum infusion, collaboration and integration, experiential learning, faculty development, infrastructure, industry collaboration and accreditation. Establishing common standardisation education guidelines has not been sufficiently completed, thus implementing green and digital transition is hindered by the lack of standardisation professionals possessing necessary knowledge on the mainstreaming EU policies. Aligning education and training programs with workforce needs, facilitating skills recognition will contribute to the transition to a green and sustainable economy. Incorporation of gender equality content is required by the EU policies, but the content isn't strictly defined for standardisation education while significant achievements have been accomplished by practitioners in terms of creating approach to gender-responsive standards. The digital skills are not specified exactly for standardisation as can be seen in the documents. The green skills policies are general and do not tackle standardisation education exclusively. The range of activities and programs to promote gender equality, green and digital transition is wide, though educational institutions, faculties, and educators have difficulties to define and deliver at least minimum requirements for gender, green, and digital skills.

Overall, there are no specific guidelines on incorporation of gender equality topics into curriculum of standardisation subjects, as well as green and digital skills are required, but not specified for standardisation education.

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